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TERRORISM LAW AND THE RIGHT TO FAIR HEARING IN AFRICAN DEMOCRACIES: NIGERIA AND KENYA PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

Terrorism has bedeviled the world, Nigeria and Kenya inclusive, for some years now. From Boko Haram Terrorist activities in the Northeastern part of Nigeria, to mind-boggling terrorist activities in Kenya even prior to September, 2013 terrorist attack on the Westgate Shopping Mall in Nairobi, and the 2014 Mpeketoni attacks. The aim of this paper is to analyze the constitutional provisions of Nigeria and Kenya that guarantee the right to fair hearing. This was in turn achieved by critically analyzing questions pertinent to the aim of the paper. The theoretical mode of research was adopted by the authors by consulting relevant materials and legislation on the subject matter. The finding reveals that the respective legislations from the two countries made provisions for fighting terrorism in their domains; nevertheless, they contain provisions that pay little or no attention to the right to fair hearing and the doctrine of separation of power. The study recommends that Kenyan Constitution be amended to guarantee absolute right to fair hearing like that of Nigeria. Terrorism Prevention Acts of both Countries be amended to be in tandem with the right to fair hearing or if the fight against terrorism worth derogation from the right to fair hearing, the Constitutions of both be amended to make right to fair hearing derogatory in respect of the fight against terrorism. Further, Kenya should learn a lesson from Nigeria to amend its

Terrorism Prevention Act to make Declaration of an Organization specified entity through Court to ensure separation of powers.

Key words: Terrorism, Terrorist, fair hearing, proscription, specified entity and Boko Haram, Africa, Democracy.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Apart from the challenges of poverty, sectarian, economic and political crises, and militancy in Niger Delta, Nigeria has also been overwhelmed with monumental challenges of terrorist attacks and activities of Boko Haram particularly in the North-Eastern Region. For years, we witnessed the vulnerability of Nigeria to terror, criminality and instability which include but not limited to the bombings of Mosques, Churches, Police Formations, Schools, Markets, Prisons (Now Correctional Service Centers) in Bauchi, Borno, Yobe and Adamawa States.¹ Other parts of the Country were also not left out as Boko Haram bombings were also experienced in the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Kano, Plateau, and Kaduna States among others.² Notable among such bombings was the bombing of the United Nations (UN) Office in Abuja by the Boko Haram insurgents which made them to be listed as terrorist organization by the United States of America (USA).

The emergence of Boko Haram and its terrorist activities in the North Eastern Region in particular and Nigeria in general, has continued to change the security architecture and dynamics of the country. The insurgent activities of Boko Haram group in its operational centers and strongholds in Nigeria have also been responsible for some instability and security challenges in the neighboring countries such as Niger, Benin Republic, Chad and Cameroon.³

In the spirited efforts of the Federal Government of Nigeria to contain the Boko Haram insurgency for the protection of lives and properties of the citizens of Nigeria and those residing within the Nigerian territory, it promulgated a legal instrument referred to as Terrorism Prevention Act, 2011, later amended in 2013. The Terrorism Prevention Act, provides measures for combating acts of terrorism and suppression of terrorism-

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¹ Akpan, F., Ekanem, O. and Olofu-Adeoye, A. (2014), "Boko Haram Insurgency and Counter Terrorism Policy in Nigeria". *Canadian Social Science*, Vol. 10, pp. 151. Available at <http://www.cscanada.net/index.php/css/article/view/4259DOI:http://dx.doi.org/10.3968/4259>. Accessed on 21st August, 2019.

² *Ibid*

³ Goyei, G., (2018), "Nigeria's Boko Haram and its Security Dynamics in the West African Sub-Region", *Journal of Language, Technology & Entrepreneurship in Africa*. Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 103.

financing, and also provides procedure for proscribing any violent group in Nigeria as a terrorist group provided the violent act of such group falls within the definition of terrorism in the Act.

Similarly, Kenya even before the September 2013 terrorist attack on Westgate Shopping Mall in Nairobi and MPEketoni 2014 terrorist attack, has been grappling with terrorist attacks such as US Embassy attack in Nairobi in 1998 killing more than two hundred people and injuring about five thousand other people.⁴ This and many more terrorist attacks prompted the Republic of Kenya to enact the Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2012 as legal instrument to guide the fight against terrorism, and it provides declaration of terror group or individual as specified entity (i.e. banned, prohibited or proscribed entity) as one of the measures for fighting terrorism but with no attention to the right to fair hearing.

The aim of this paper is to analyze the provision of the Nigerian and Kenya's Constitution that guarantee right to fair hearing and to determine whether specified entity or organizations are accorded the right to be heard before being proscribed or tagged as terrorist organization. This paper employs doctrinal legal research as the methodology. In order to accomplish the above objectives, this paper examines the concept and nature of terrorism; discusses right to fair hearing under the Nigerian and Kenyan Constitutions; examines the procedure for proscription under the Terrorism Laws of Nigeria and Kenya.

2.0 THE CONCEPT AND NATURE OF TERRORISM

The term terrorism is neither definite nor definitive. Put differently, there have been a lot of controversies among the legal luminaries and jurists as to the meaning of the term terrorism, and many definitions of terrorism have been offered. There is little agreement on what constitutes terrorism and who practices terrorism even among academics, notwithstanding the myriad of militaries, judicial systems, intelligence agencies and governmental organizations that deal with the term terrorism from their point of view.⁵

Terrorism is defined to mean the use of various violent means for political purpose; to unleash deliberate violent attacks on civilians, police, military and other security

⁴ O'Grady, S., (2020), "For Kenyans Militant Group Al-Shabab is a Deadly Threat That Won't Back Down". Available at www.washingtonpost.com (Accessed on 30th April, 2020).

⁵ Adibe, E. (2016), "Revisiting the Problem of Definition of Terrorism as a Criminal Act: A Critical Analysis", *African Journal of Criminal Law and Jurisprudence*. Vol. 1, p. 141.

formations coupled with massive destruction of government facilities and civil properties such as oil and power installations, police formations, Prisons, Churches, Mosques etc., with intention to intimidate or coerce a civil society, to influence the policy of government by intimidation or coercion, and affect the conduct of government by assassination or kidnapping.⁶

Article 1 (3) of the African Union Convention on the Prevention and Combating Terrorism, 1999 defines terrorism to mean:

(a) Any act which is a violation of the criminal laws of a state Party and which may endanger the life, physical integrity or freedom of, or cause serious injury or death to, any person, any number or group of persons or causes or may cause damage to public or private property, natural resources, environmental or cultural heritage and is calculated or intended to:

(i) Intimidate, put in fear, force, coerce or induce any government, body, institution, the general public or any segment thereof, to do or abstain from doing any act, or to adopt or abandoned a particular standpoint, or to act according to certain principles; or

(ii) Disrupt any public service, the delivery of any essential service to the public or to create public emergency; or

(iii) Create general insurrection in a state.

(b) Any promotion, sponsoring, contribution to, command, aid, incitement, encouragement, attempt, threat, conspiracy, organizing, or procurement of any person, with the intent to commit any act referred to in paragraph (a)((i) to (iii).

It is submitted that, any act, commission or omission which qualifies as a terrorist act is listed in the above legal instrument of the African Union, and any person natural or artificial that commits or threatens to commit any of the acts listed therein will be considered as

⁶ Abimbola, J. O. and Adesote, S. A. (2012), "Domestic Terrorism and Boko Haram Insurgency in Nigeria, Issues and Trends: A Historical Discourse", *Journal of Arts and Contemporary Society*, Vol. 4, p. 14.

terrorist and liable to be punished accordingly on conviction. However, by the provisions of the same AU Convention, notwithstanding the provisions of Article I above, any struggle or movement by the people in accordance with the principles of international law for their liberation or self-determination, including armed struggles against colonialism, occupation, aggression and domination by foreign forces shall not be considered as terrorist acts or acts of terrorism.⁷ According to Francis Ojeh and Segun Adesanya, this proviso or differentiation is necessary because of the dynamic nature of the African continent where call for accountable and responsible government may likely lead to demonstrations and self-determination.⁸

The Nigerian Terrorism Prevention Act (TPA)⁹ also provides for the conceptual definition of terrorism when it provides thus:

In this Section, "act of terrorism" means an act which is deliberately done with malice, aforethought and which

(a) may seriously harm or damage a country or an international organization;

(b) is intended or can reasonably be regarded as having been intended to-

(i) unduly compel a government or international organization to perform or abstain from performing any act;

(ii) seriously intimidate a population;

(iii) seriously destabilize or destroy the fundamental political, constitutional, economic or social structures of a country or an international organization, or

(iv) otherwise influence such government or international organization by intimidation or coercion; and

(c) involves or cause, as the case may be -

⁷ African Union (1999). African Union Convention on the Prevention and Combating of Terrorism 1999, Art. III (2). Available at: <https://www.african-court.org/wpafc/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/13-OAU-CONVENTION-ON-TERRORISM.pdf>.

⁸ Ojeh, F and Adesanya, S. (2018). "The Need for Human Security Approach in Combating Terrorism in Nigeria", Ahmadu Bello University Law Journal, Vol. 38, P. 2

⁹ Terrorism Prevention Act 2011 (as amended), S. 1(2)

- (i) an attack upon a person's life which may cause serious bodily harm or death;*
- (ii) kidnapping of a person;*
- (iii) destruction to a government or public facility, transport system, an infrastructural facility including an information system, a fixed platform located on the continental shelf, public place or private property likely to endanger human life or result in major economic loss;*
- (iv) the seizure of an aircraft, ship or other means of public or goods transport and diversion or the use of such means of transportation for any of the purpose in paragraph (b) (iv) of this subsection;*
- (v) the manufacture, possession, acquisition, transport, supply or use of weapons, explosives or of nuclear, biological or chemical weapons, as well as research into, and development of biological and chemical weapons without lawful authority;*
- (vi) the release of dangerous substance or causing of fire. Explosions or floods, the effect of which is to endanger human life;*
- (vii) interference with or disruption of the supply of water, power or any other fundamental natural resources, the effect of which is to endanger life.*
- (d) an act or omission in or outside Nigeria which constitute an offence within the scope of a counter terrorism protocols and conventions duly ratified by Nigeria.*

However, the Terrorism Prevention Act, 2011 is amended in 2013 by Terrorism (Prevention) (Amendment) Act, 2013 which widens the scope of terrorism offences under the Act. It provides that:

A person or body corporate that knowingly in or outside Nigeria directly or indirectly does, attempts or threatens any act of terrorism, commits an act preparatory to or in furtherance of an of terrorism, omits to do anything that is reasonably necessary to prevent an act of terrorism, assist or facilitates the activities of persons engaged in an act of terrorism or is an accessory to any offence under the act, participates as an accomplice in or contributes to the commission of any act of terrorism or offences

under the Act, assists, facilitates, organizes or directs the activities of persons or organizations engaged in any act of terrorism, is an accessory to any act of terrorism, or incites, promises or induces any other persons by any means whatsoever to commit any act of terrorism or any of the offences referred to in the Act, commits an offence under the Act and liable on conviction to maximum of death sentence.¹⁰

Also, the interpretation Section of the Kenyan Prevention of Terrorism Act, defines terrorist act to mean an act or threat of action-

- (a) which-*
 - (i) involves the use of violence against a person;*
 - (ii) endangers the life of a person, other than the person committing the action;*
 - (iii) creates a serious risk to the health or safety of the public or a section of the public;*
 - (iv) results in serious damage to property;*
 - (iv) involves the use of firearms or explosives;*
 - (v) involves the release of any dangerous, hazardous, toxic or radioactive substance or microbial or other biological agent or toxin into the environment;*
 - (vi) interferes with an electronic system resulting in the disruption of the provision of communication, financial, transport or other essential services;*
 - (vii) interferes or disrupts the provision of essential or emergency services;*
 - (viii) prejudices national security or public safety; and*
- (b) which is carried out with the aim of -*
 - (i) intimidating or causing fear amongst members of the public or a section of the public; or*
 - (ii) intimidating or compelling the Government or international organization to do, or refrain from any act; or*

¹⁰ Terrorism (Prevention) (Amendment) Act 2013, s. 2(c)

(iii) destabilizing the religious, political Constitutional, economic or social institutions of a country, or an international organization:

Provided that an act which disrupts any services and is committed in pursuance of a protest, demonstration or stoppage of work shall be deemed not to be a terrorist act within the meaning of this definition so long as the act is not intended to result in any harm referred to in paragraph (a)(i) to (iv).¹¹

It is observed that, from the above definitions of terrorism offered by the Nigerian and Kenyan legal instruments, the definitions of terrorism by the Nigerian Terrorism Prevention Act, 2011 is more comprehensive and wider than the definition in the Kenyan Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2012 as Nigerian TPA makes aiding and abetting or omission to prevent an act of terrorism within or outside Nigeria and possession or transportation of arms or explosives without lawful authority to be terrorist acts.

It should also be noted that under the Kenyan Prevention of Terrorism Act, disruption of any service pursuant to protest or demonstration, shall not be a terrorist act if it is not intended to result into violence against person, endangering the life of a person other than the person committing the act of such disruption, creating serious risk to the health or safety of the public or Section thereof, and causing serious damage to property.¹²

3.0 THE RIGHT TO FAIR HEARING UNDER THE NIGERIAN AND KENYAN CONSTITUTIONS
The Supreme Court of Nigeria in the case of *Gyang v. C.O.P Lagos State*¹³ defined fair hearing when it held thus:

The principle of fair hearing as enshrined in section 36 (1) of the Constitution does not necessarily mean an oral hearing. What is required is that every party to dispute is given an opportunity to state his case. Each party must know the case being made given against him and given an opportunity to react thereto...

The provisions of Sections 36 (1) and (2) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) provided for the right to fair hearing as follows:

¹¹ Prevention of Terrorism Act 2012, s. 2

¹² Ibid

¹³ (2014) 3 NWLR (pt.1395) 547

- (1) *In the determination of his civil rights and obligations, including any question or determination by or against any government or authority, a person shall be entitled to a fair hearing within reasonable time by a court or other tribunal established by law and constituted in such manner as secure its independence and impartiality.*
- (2) *Without prejudice to the foregoing provisions of this section, a law shall not be invalidated by reason only that it confers on any government or authority power to determine questions arising in the administration of a law that affects or may affect the civil right and obligations of any person if such law-*
 - (a) *Provides for opportunity for the person whose rights and obligations may be affected to make representations to the administering authority before that authority makes the decisions affecting that person; and*
 - (b) *Contains no provisions making the determination of the administering authority final and conclusive.*

From the above provisions of the 1999 Nigerian constitution, it is not only courts that are bound to observe and adhere to the principle of fair hearing, administrative bodies or tribunals acting judicially in the determination of or imposition of any decision that is likely to affect the civil rights or obligation of any person are also bound to observe strictly the principles of fair hearing. The principle of right to fair hearing is being expressed in the Latin maxim “audi alterem partem” which means “hear the other side” or hear both parties and “Nemo iudex in causa sua” meaning no person should be a judge in his own case.

It should be noted that any decision or order made that violates the principle of fair hearing against any person cannot stand and must be set aside by a court of law competent to do so. In other words, the right to fair hearing, being a constitutional right under the Nigerian constitution, the breach of it by any court, tribunal or administrative authority in any trial or inquiry makes such trial or inquiry a nullity.¹⁴

¹⁴ Atobatele v. Faresu (2013) 1 NWLR (Pt. 1335) 349 at 356 R. 7; Aduba, J. N and Oguche, S. (2014), “Key Issues in Nigerian Constitutional law”, Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies. P. 182

It is also worthy of note that, the Nigerian constitution apart from the right to fair hearing in Section 36, also provides for the right to life,¹⁵ right to dignity of human person,¹⁶ right to personal liberty,¹⁷ right to private and family life,¹⁸ right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion,¹⁹ right to freedom of expression and the press,²⁰ right to peaceful assembly and association,²¹ right to freedom of movement,²² right to freedom from discrimination,²³ and right to acquire and own immoveable property anywhere in Nigeria.²⁴

However, the same Constitution places limitations on these rights with the exception to right to dignity of human person in Section 34, right to fair hearing in Section 36. It provides that nothing in Sections 37, 38, 39, 40, and 41 of the Constitution shall invalidate any law which is reasonably justifiable in a democratic society- in the interest of defense, public safety, public order, public morality or public health; or for the purpose of protecting the rights and freedom of other persons.²⁵ It is further provided that an Act of the National assembly shall not be invalidated reason being that it provides for the taking during period of emergency, of measures that derogates from the provisions of Sections 33 or 35 of the constitution, but no such measures shall be taken pursuant to such Act during any period of emergency except to the extent that such measures are reasonably justifiable for the purpose of dealing with such situation that exists during the period of emergency.²⁶

It is clear from the above that, the provisions of Section 36 (1) of the Constitution which provides for the right to fair hearing is not mentioned among the rights to be derogated from in the interest of public safety, public defense, during period of emergency or in the name of the fight against terrorism, hence it signifies that the right to fair hearing cannot be derogated from in whatever circumstances. This is express in the legal maxim

¹⁵ The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), s. 33

¹⁶ *Ibid* s. 34

¹⁷ *Ibid* s. 35

¹⁸ *Ibid* s. 37

¹⁹ *Ibid* s. 38

²⁰ *Ibid* s. 39

²¹ *Ibid* s. 40

²² *Ibid* s. 41

²³ *Ibid* s. 42

²⁴ *Ibid* s. 43

²⁵ *Ibid* s. 45 (1) (a) and (b)

²⁶ *Ibid* s. 45 (2)

Expressio Unium Personae Vel Rei, Est Exclusio Alterium which means the mention of one thing without mentioning the other, means it is excluded.

Equally, the Kenyan Constitution 2010 provides for the right to fair hearing in chapter four, Article 50 (1) and it provide thus:

Every person has the right to have any dispute that can be resolved by the application of law decided in a fair and public hearing before a court or, if appropriate, another independent and impartial tribunal or body.

Apart from the right to fair hearing, the Constitution of Kenya also guarantees some fundamental rights such as right to life,²⁷ equality and freedom from discrimination,²⁸ right to human dignity,²⁹ right to freedom and security of the person,³⁰ freedom against slavery, servitude and force labor,³¹ right to privacy³² right to freedom of conscience, religion, belief and opinion,³³ freedom of expression, freedom of the media, access to information, freedom of association, freedom of assembly, demonstration, picketing and petition, political rights, freedom of movement and residence, right to property, right to clean and healthy environment, economic and social rights, right to language and culture, right to family, consumer rights, and right to fair administrative action among others.³⁴

However, because of the importance attached to the right to fair hearing, by the provisions of Article 25 the Constitution of Kenya, the right to fair trial along with the freedom from torture and cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, the rights to freedom from slavery and servitude, and the right to an order of habeas corpus shall not be limited or derogated from, as opposed to other rights provided by the bill of rights of the Constitution of Kenya, that can be limited or derogated from when the circumstances warrant.

It is submitted that, even the non- derogatory status of the right to fair hearing under Article 25 of the Constitution of Kenya is not absolute, reason being that, the provision of Article 58

²⁷ Kenyan Constitution 2010 Art. 26

²⁸ Ibid Art. 27

²⁹ Ibid Art. 28

³⁰ Ibid Art. 29

³¹ Ibid Art. 30

³² Ibid Art. 31

³³ Ibid Art. 32

³⁴ Ibid Art. 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 46, 47.

which provides for and deals with the declaration of state of emergency in Kenya, provides that after declaration of a state of emergency, legislation enacted or any action taken pursuant to such declaration, may not permit the indemnification of the State, or any person in respect of any unlawful act or omission. This signifies that, if in the course of act or omission for the purpose of state of emergency, the right of any person to fair trial or fair hearing is violated, he may not be compensated for such invasion into or violation of his right to fair hearing. This is contrary to the position under the 1999 Nigerian Constitution which makes the non-derogatory status of the right to fair hearing very absolute in whatever situations and circumstances.

4.0 THE PROCEDURE FOR PROSCRIPTION UNDER THE TERRORISM LAWS OF NIGERIA AND KENYA

The term proscription has been defined to mean the act of prohibiting; the state of being prohibited. It also means a prohibition or restriction.³⁵ The Terrorism Prevention Act of Nigeria defined a proscribed organization to mean an organization which has been declared to be a proscribed organization under Section 2 of the Act, and includes a group which has been declared to be an international terrorist group under Section 9 of the Act; traceable to a terrorist act and includes funds irrespective of the person in whose names such proceeds are standing or in whose possession they are found.³⁶

Even before the coming into force of the Terrorism Prevention Act on the 3rd day of June, 2011, there were incidences of proscription of some organizations by the federal government of Nigeria. There was for instance proscription of Academic Staff Union of Nigerian Universities (ASUU) by the military administration of General Babangida in 1987.³⁷ Also, the Federal Government once proscribed the National Union of Nigerian Students (NUNS) before it later metamorphosed into the present National Association of Nigerian Students (NANS).³⁸

³⁵ Garner, B. A., (2004), 'Proscription', Black's Law Dictionary, Thomson Business. P. 1341

³⁶ TPA 2011 (As amended), s. 40

³⁷ Samuel, O. A., Emenike, E. I., and Eze, O. O., (2017), "Causes, Effects and Management of Asuu Strikes in Nigeria 2003-2013". *Journal of Research and Development*, Vol. 3, Issue 3, P. 15. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325546327_Causes_Effects_and_Management_of_ASUU_Strikes_in_Nigeria_2003-2013. Accessed on 29th September, 2019.

³⁸ Tribune Online (2019), "FG's Proscription of IMAN". Available at <https://tribuneonline.com/fgs-proscription-of-imn/> accessed on 30th September, 2019

After the coming in to force of the Terrorism Prevention Act, there was proscription of the Independent People of Biafra (IPOB) as a terrorist organization by the Federal Government of Nigeria.³⁹ So also, sequel to the violent activities of the Islamic Movement in Nigeria (IMN) led by Sheikh El-Zakzaky, and the recent faceoff between the security agencies and the said Islamic Movement of Nigeria (IMN), the Federal Government of Nigeria, proscribed IMN as a terrorist organization.⁴⁰ This was pursuant to the Court order secured by the Office of the Attorney General of the Federation by virtue of the provision of the Terrorism Prevention Act. The Act,⁴¹ which laid down procedure for proscription of an organization as terrorist as follows:

- (1) *two or more persons associate for the purpose of or where an organization engages in –*
 - (a) *Participating Where or collaborating in act of terrorism;*
 - (b) *Promoting, encouraging or exhorting others to commit an act of terrorism; or*
 - (c) *Setting up or pursuing acts of terrorism, the judge in Chambers may on the application made by the Attorney General, National Security Adviser or Inspector General of Police on the approval of the President; declare any entity to be a proscribed organization and the notice should be published in official gazette.*
- (2) *An order made under sub-section (1) of this section shall be published in official gazette, in two national newspapers and at such other places as the judge in Chambers may determine.*
- (3) *A publication made under sub-section (2) of this section shall contain such relevant particulars as the judge in Chambers may specify:*

³⁹ Adanger, Z. (2018), "Proscription of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB and the Politics of Terrorism in Nigeria", *The Journal of Jurisprudence and Contemporary Issues*. Vol. 10, Issue 1. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publications/332241912_PROSCRIPTION_OF_THE_POLITICS_OF_TERRORISM_IN_NIGERIA. Accessed on 29th September, 2019 at 9:20 pm.

⁴⁰ Tribune Online (2019), "FG's Proscription of IMAN". Available at <https://tribuneonlineng.com/fgs-proscription-of-imn/> accessed on 30th September, 2019

⁴¹ TPA 2011 s. 2

(i) a person who belongs or professes to belong to a proscribed organization commits an offence under this Act and shall on conviction be liable to imprisonment for a maximum term of 20 years;

(ii) for the avoidance of doubts, political parties should not be regarded as proscribed organizations and nobody should be treated as such because of his or her political beliefs.

It can be inferred from the provisions of Terrorism Prevention Act above, that where the government intends to proscribe any organization whose activities fall within the definition of an act of terrorism under the Act, it is for either the Attorney General of the Federation, the National Security Adviser or Inspector General of Police subject to or with the approval of the President to apply to a judge in Chambers (i.e. ex-parte), behind or without notice to the organization sought to be proscribed. This is a flagrant violation of the right to fair hearing of such organization and its members thereof as guaranteed by Section 36 (1) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended)

The Constitution of Nigeria provides and guarantees right to fair hearing thus:

In the determination of his civil rights and obligations, including any question or determination by or against any government or authority, a person shall be entitle to a fair hearing within reasonable time by a court or other tribunal established by law and constituted in such manner as to secure its independence and impartiality.⁴²

Although, the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) guarantees fundamental rights in the Sections of Chapter IV,⁴³ as earlier said, it upholds any law that derogates and places some limitations on some of those guaranteed fundamental rights in the interest of defense, public safety, public order, public morality or

⁴² Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), S.36 (1)

⁴³ The provisions of sections 33 provides for right to life, sections 34 provides for right to dignity of human person, and 35 provides for the right to personal liberty, section 36 provides for the right to fair hearing, Sections 37 provides for the right to family and private life, Section 38 provides for the right to freedom thought, conscience and religion, Section 39 provides for the right to freedom of expressions, Section 40 provides for the right to peaceful assembly and association, section 41 provides for the right of movement, Section 42 provides for the right against discrimination, and section 43 provides for the right to own immovable property.

public health or for the purpose of protecting the right of others, but it places no limitation to right to fair hearing.⁴⁴

The provision of Section 45 provides that:

(1) Nothing in sections 37, 38, 39, 40 and 41 of this Constitution shall invalidate any law that is reasonably justifiable in a democratic society-

(a) In the interest of defense, public safety, public order, public morality or public health; or

(b) for the purpose of protecting the rights and freedom of other persons. (2)

An Act of the National Assembly shall not be invalidated by reason only that it provides for the taking, during periods of emergency, of measures that derogate from the provisions of Section 33 or 35 of this Constitution; but no such measures shall be taken in pursuance of any Act during any periods of emergency save to the extent that those measures are reasonably justifiable for the purpose of dealing with the situation that exists during that period of emergency:

Provided that nothing in this Section shall authorize any derogation from the provisions of Section 33 of this Constitution except in respect of death resulting from acts of war or authorize any derogation from the provisions of Section 36(8) of this Constitution.

(3) In this section, a "period of emergency" means any period during which there is in force a Proclamation of state of emergency declared by the President in exercise of the power conferred on him under Section 305 of this Constitution.

The above provisions allow for the derogation from the respect and protection of the most cherished fundamental human rights of private and family life, right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, right to freedom of expression, right to freedom of peaceful assembly and association, and right to freedom of movement and right to personal liberty by any law that is reasonably justifiable in a democratic society in the interest of defense, public order, public safety, public morality or public health.

⁴⁴ Ibid. S.45

In the case *F.R.A Rotimi Williams v. Majekodunmi (No 1)*⁴⁵ there was a declaration of state of emergency in the Western Region in 1962, the Defendant was appointed Sole Administrator of the Western Region after the removal of Chief Akintola as Premier Western Region, and pursuant to Emergency Powers Act, 1961 some regulations were made which included Emergency Powers (Restriction Orders) Regulations that empowered the Defendant to cause Restriction Orders to be issued and served on individuals restricting their movement to a defined area to be stated in the Order. The Plaintiff was served with restriction Order restricting his movements to a distance of three miles from a certain address in Abeokuta. It was in the light of this fact that the Plaintiff approached the Supreme Court seeking for an injunctive order against the Defendant, and a declaration that the Emergency Powers (Restriction Orders) Regulation 1962 was ultra vires, illegal and unconstitutional.

The Supreme Court declared that the restriction order of 29th May, 1962 which ordered the Plaintiff to remain within a distance of three miles from No 3 Abeokuta Road in the township of Abeokuta was not reasonably justifiable.

Therefore, pursuant to the provisions of Section 45 of the Constitution above, Terrorism Prevention Act shall not be invalidated on the ground that it provided for measures that derogates from those rights specified by the Section on the ground of public safety, public order etc. However, having a cursory look at the provisions of Section 45, while it specifies the fundamental rights to be derogated which includes the right to life which is not only important but the mother of all rights, no mention was made of the right to right to fair hearing. This signifies without doubt that the right to fair hearing guaranteed by the Constitution of Nigeria is not amenable to derogation in whatever situation.

On the other hand, the republic of Kenya as discussed above, being bedeviled with terrorist activities, was prompted to promulgate the Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2012 as a legal instrument to guide the Kenyan Government in the fight against terrorism. One of the measures taken in the fight against terrorism in Kenya under the Prevention of Terrorism

⁴⁵ (1962) ALL NLR 410.

Act is the declaration of terrorist organizations as specified entity which is equivalent to Nigeria's proscription of an organization as a terrorist group.

The provision of Section 2 of the Prevention of terrorism Act⁴⁶ defines entity to mean a person, group of persons, trust, partnership, fund or an unincorporated association or organization, while specified entity to mean an entity in respect of which an order under Section 3 has been made. The provision of Section 3 provides for the procedure for declaration of an entity or organization as specified entity by specified entity order through the office of the Inspector General of the Kenyan Police. It provides thus:

(1) Where the Inspector General has reasonable grounds to believe that-

(a) An entity has-

(i) Committed or prepared to commit;

(ii) Attempted to commit; or

(iii) Participated in or facilitated the commission of,

A terrorist act; or

(b) An entity is acting-

(i) On behalf of;

(ii) At the direction of; or

(iii) In association with,

an entity referred to in paragraph (a),

he may recommend to the cabinet Secretary that an order be made under subsection (3)

in respect of that entity.

(2) Before making a recommendation under subsection (1), the Inspector General shall afford the affected entity an opportunity demonstrates why it should not be declared as a specified entity.

(3) Upon receipt of the recommendation under subsection (1), the Cabinet Secretary may, where is satisfied that there are reasonable grounds to support a recommendation under subsection (1), declare, by order

⁴⁶ PTA 2011

published in the Gazette, the entity in respect of which the recommendation has been made to be a specified entity.

- (4) The Cabinet Secretary shall, subject to subsection (5), inform the entity in respect of which the order is made, in writing, of his decision under subsection (3) together with reasons for arriving at that decision, within a period of seven days from the date of declaring the entity a specified entity.

From the provision of Section 3 above, whenever the Inspector General of Police of Kenya has reasons or grounds to believe that, an entity or organization has committed, prepared or attempted to commit, participated in or facilitated the commission of a terrorist act, or an entity or organization is acting on behalf of, on the direction of or in association any entity referred to in paragraph (a) of subsection (1), he may after affording an opportunity to the entity affected to demonstrate or show cause why it should not be declared as a specified entity, recommend to the Cabinet Secretary that an order be made declaring such entity as specified entity under subsection (3) of this Section 3. The Cabinet Secretary may upon the receipt of the recommendation from the Inspector General of Police, and being satisfied that there are reasonable grounds to support such recommendation, exercise his power under subsection (3) and by order published in the Gazette declare the entity in respect of the said recommendation made to him by Inspector General, to be a specified entity, and thereafter inform the entity affected of such decision in writing together with the reasons thereof within seven days of such decisions.

It is submitted that, the powers of the Inspector General to whenever he has reason to believe that an entity has committed, prepared or attempted to commit, or participated in or facilitated the commission of terrorist act, and after affording opportunity to such entity to show cause why it should not be declared as specified entity, recommend to the Cabinet Secretary for declaration of such affected entity as specified entity, made him a judge in his own case contrary to the principle in the legal maxim: *Nemo iudex in causa sua* which is a pillar of fair hearing guaranteed by Article 50 of the Kenyan Constitution. Also the power of the Cabinet Secretary to upon the recommendation of the Inspector General, declare any entity as specified entity without affording opportunity to such affected entity to make presentation or show cause why it should not be declared a specified entity, is a violation

of the right to fair hearing of such entity guaranteed by Article 50(1) of the Kenyan Constitution 2010.

The provision of subsection (5) of Section 3 above, empowers the entity that is declared specified entity by the Cabinet Secretary to apply to the Inspector General for the revocation of such order under subsection (3). If on the application made under subsection (5) the inspector General is satisfied that, there are reasonable grounds for making such application, recommend to the Cabinet Secretary for revocation of such order, and if there are no reasonable grounds for making the application to the satisfaction of the Inspector General, he shall reject the application and inform the applicant of such decision within sixty days of the receipt of the application.⁴⁷

A specified entity which is aggrieved by the decisions of the Inspector General in rejecting its application under subsection (6), may apply to the High Court for a review of that decision within a period of sixty days from the date of the receipt of that decision.⁴⁸ In determining such application, the Court may receive and determine in chambers, all information considered by the Cabinet Secretary in arriving at his decision under subsection (3) and any other evidence submitted by the Inspector General, any institution or agency of a foreign or international organization that is relevant to the determination of such application, and may receive in evidence, any information obtained by the Government, any institution or agency of a foreign State that it may consider necessary in determining the application. The Court shall also provide the applicant with the statement of the information available to Court to enable the applicant to be reasonably informed of the reason (s) for the decision, but without disclosing any information the disclosure of which in the opinion of the Court, could be prejudicial to national security or endanger any person, and shall give the applicant reasonable opportunity to be heard.⁴⁹

The Court may also on the application of the Cabinet Secretary, consider any evidence or information adduced by him before the Court in the absence of the applicant or the Counsel representing him where the disclosure of that information or evidence would be

⁴⁷ PTA 2012, s. 3(6) (a)(b)

⁴⁸ Ibid s. 3(7)

⁴⁹ Ibid s. 3(8)(a)(b)(c) and (d)

prejudicial to national security or endanger the safety of any person, and the Court may if satisfied that there are no reasonable grounds for declaring an entity as specified entity, make an order for the revocation of the order made by the Cabinet Secretary in respect of the applicant.⁵⁰

The Cabinet Secretary shall, in consultation with the Inspector General of Police, and within the period of twelve months from the commencement of the (i.e. Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2012) and in every subsequent year, review all the orders made under subsection (3) of Section 3 to determine whether the grounds for declaring such an entity as a specified entity apply with respect to that entity and may revoke the order or such orders as he deems appropriate, and he may also where he reasonable grounds to believe that a specified entity is operating wholly or in part under a name that is not specified in the order or under different name from that specified in the order, direct that the entity be treated as a specified entity under the Act, and that the name of that entity which is not specified in that schedule be treated as another name for the specified entity.⁵¹

It is submitted that, the power of the Inspector General to receive an application from the affected entity for the revocation of an order by the Cabinet Secretary declaring it as specified entity, and to accept or reject same for recommendation to the Cabinet Secretary based on his state of believe and satisfaction as to whether or not there are reasonable grounds for such application, made him a judge in his own case in violation of the right to fair hearing of the affected entity. Also the power of the High Court to while considering an application for review of the decisions of the Inspector General in refusing the application for revocation of the order under subsection 3(i.e. an order declaring it as specified entity by the Cabinet Secretary) by the entity affected, on the application of the Cabinet Secretary hear any evidence or information adduced by him in the absence of the applicant or the counsel representing him when the disclosure of such information would be prejudicial to the national security, is a gross violation of the applicant right to fair hearing under Article 50 (1) of the Kenyan Constitution, 2010.

⁵⁰ Ibid s. 3(9) and (10)

⁵¹ Ibid s. 3(11) and (12)

It is further argument of this paper, that conferring power on the Cabinet Secretary who is the Secretary for the time being responsible for internal security in Kenya, and therefore part of the executive arm of Kenyan government, to on the recommendation of the Inspector General declare a person or organization a specified entity, is not only violation of the right to fair hearing of the affected entity, but also usurpation of the powers of the judicial arm of Kenyan government which is against the doctrine of separation of power not only under Article 1(3) of the Kenyan Constitution or Constitutions of African democracies, but also Constitutions of most countries of the world.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This study examined the nature and concept of terrorism; the right to fair hearing under the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended), and the Constitution of Kenya 2010; procedure for proscribing a group as terrorist organization under the Terrorism Prevention Act, 2011(as amended) and the procedure for the declaration of an entity as specified entity under the Kenyan Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2012 as well as the right to fair hearing guaranteed by Section 36 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) and Article 50 of the Constitution of Kenya, 2010. It is found that the right to fair hearing is not one of the rights to be derogated in the interest public safety and public order in both Nigeria and Kenya.

It is observed that both the Constitution of the Federal republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) and the Constitution of Kenya, 2010 provide and guarantee the right to fair hearing in Section 36 and Article 50 respectively. The finding of this study shows that the provisions of Section 45 of the Nigerian Constitution 1999 makes the right to fair hearing absolute and non-derogatory in whatever circumstances whereas the provision of Article 25 of the Kenyan Constitution 2010 did not make the right to fair hearing absolute and non-derogatory. That is to say the right to fair hearing under Kenyan Constitution is not absolute in that it can be inferred from the provisions of Article 58 when the right to fair hearing of any person is violated owing to the put in place during state of emergency, such person may not be indemnified.

However, the result reveals that both countries in the spirit of the fight against terrorism promulgated anti-terrorism laws which negate the right to fair hearing guaranteed by the

Constitutions of countries. The provisions of Section 2 of the Nigerian Terrorism Prevention Act, 2012 provides the procedure for proscribing a group as terrorist organization by the Federal High Court, on the application of either the Attorney General of the Federation, National Security Adviser or Inspector General of Police, but without affording the organization or group affected to be heard and make presentation in respect of such application. This negates the right to fair hearing of such organization or group. Also, the provision of Section 3 of the Kenyan Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2012 empowers the Cabinet Secretary, to on the recommendation of the Inspector General of Police declare an entity as specified entity without affording the affected entity an opportunity to be heard and make presentation in respect of such order. Not only that, the provisions of Section 3(9) and (10) of the same Act of Kenya empowers the High Court to while considering the application by the affected entity against the rejection of its application for revocation of the order made against it under Section 3 (3) on the application of the Cabinet Secretary receive any evidence or information in the absence of the applicant entity or the counsel representing it.

It is also observed that, while the provisions of Section 2 of the Nigerian Terrorism Prevention Act, 2011 confers power on the Federal High Court to, on the application of either Attorney General of the Federation, National Security Adviser or Inspector General of Police, make an order proscribing a group or organization as terrorist group or organization. Equally, the provisions of Section 3(3) of the Kenyan Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2012 empowers the Cabinet Secretary who is part of the Executive arm of the Kenyan Government to on the recommendation of Inspector General declare an entity as a specified entity. This is against the doctrine of separation of power under Articles 1 (3), 93, 94, 129 (1), and 159 (1) of the Constitution of Kenya, 2010.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the afore stated observations, it is recommended that the provisions of the Nigerian Terrorism Prevention Act, 2011, particularly Section 2, and the provisions of the Kenyan Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2012 particularly Section 3 be amended to make the procedure for proscribing an organization as a terrorist organization and declaring an entity as specified entity, to be in tandem and compliance with the right to fair hearing

guaranteed by Sections 36 of the Nigerian Constitution 1999 and Article 50 of the Constitution of Kenya, 2010. Also, the Republic of Kenya should learn a lesson from Nigerian Constitution and amend their Constitution to make the right to fair hearing completely absolute even during state of emergency. In the alternative, if the fight against terrorism is worth derogating from the right to fair hearing, the provision of Section 45 of the Nigerian Constitution 1999, and Articles 24 and 25 of the Constitution of Kenya, 2010, should be amended to make the right to fair not absolute and derogatory in the fight against terrorism.

It is further recommended that, the Republic of Kenya should learn a lesson from Nigeria to amend the provisions of Prevention of Terrorism Act, 2012, to make declaration of an entity as specified entity by the court of law in the spirit of the doctrine of separation of power.